

Evolution of Educational Management and Its Impact on Society

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ABSTRACT: It is recognized that education is the field with the oldest history throughout the science perimeter. Education has been a special concern and a major concern for all social categories throughout history. The ultimate goal of education has been and remains to ensure the inner peace of man in all circumstances of life. Beyond the information received, man needs to know what to do and how to do in the context of a correct understanding of reality.

The hope of people lies in the good education they provide to every citizen. Through this education, each person must be prepared to live a complete life and to be able to fulfill all the kinds of activities he needs in life. In this sense, it is very important for education to have clear objectives; without this objective, the whole educational process being inefficient. This article highlights the evolution of educational management over the course of history and its impact on society. At the same time, some recommendations will be presented for the effective use of the fantastic potential of the company.

KEYWORDS: management, education, evolution, society, school

The cumulative systematization of knowledge and experience has led in all fields, including education, to the emergence, formulation and consolidation of science. Scientific systematization induces coherence, rigor and structure, ensuring a better communication.

The main models of approach and interpretation in management science and their progressive outline over time, presented by O. Nicolescu (1993, 46-48), E. Mihuleac (1994, 161-168) and I. Petrescu (1993, 14-20), are:

“Classical School”: highlights the role of human resources in providing, organizing, deciding, coordinating, controlling activities, achieving higher returns, predominantly applied in the economic field. (The primary merit of the classical school is the substantial contribution to the shaping of management science, the delimitation of managerial and organizational functions and the development of scientific management principles).

“School of Functional Management”: outlines a system of knowledge, principles, and theories applicable to the achievement of managerial functions as essential dimensions but with the minimization of the human factor. (The advantages of this school are the rigorous division of tasks into compartments, which gives them autonomy. A disadvantage of this school is the underestimation of relations between compartments.)

“Empirical School”: is concerned with compliance with normality as a key to efficiency, profit growth, productivity, as well as management’s concern for objectives, decentralization, motivation, competitive climate. (Empirical management emerged with the division of labor and human livelihood in organized groups. The advantage of this school is that it is based on studying reality, successes and failures, offering the possibility of choosing a technique, methods in comparable situations. The disadvantage of this school is that, in the conditions of a changing environment, it has many risks).

“School of Human Relations”: puts in the center of leadership problem solving by using interpersonal relationships, group collaboration being a priority in relation to individual activity. (Representatives of this school have introduced behavioral elements in management theory in an integrating aspect. One of the basic theses of the School of Human Relations is the idea of a participatory system designed to replace the authoritarian management and control system developed by the classical school.)

“School of Social Systems”: insists on the role of subsystems in the organization, which are then integrated around objectives, decisions, the dominant role of communication networks, motivation, and continuous stimulation. (It treats relationships in terms of social relations. It is the dominant current in contemporary management theory).

“Behavioral System”: promotes the thesis of adapting people to the specifics of an organization and work, using psychological, sociological concepts and methods, emphasizing the role of organizing, coordinating, motivating / motivating, evaluating functions. (Through this school it is desired to train the personality to express through appropriate behavior within society).

“Quantitative School”: highlights contributions from other exact disciplines for the introduction of quantitative methods and techniques in the coordination and organization of the educational system. (This school is characterized by the rigorous approach to management phenomena and processes, by increasing the degree of substantiation of decisions using the mathematical and statistical tools. The essence of this school is the presumption that techniques and statistics can be used to improve managerial decision-making and problem-solving. The main merit of the quantitative school is to provide a substantiation of decisions and actions).

“Decision Theory School”: By using operational research, it reports management to the selection of several possible variants of a particular course of action. (The decision-making process consists of a series of distinct phases between which there is no simple, sequential relationship. At present, in the complex society in which we operate, characterized by the manifestation of a multitude of contradictory economic and social factors, the process of substantiation, implementing high-performance decisions - in all areas of activity and at all hierarchical levels - is an objective necessity.)

“School of Communication Systems”: sees the manager as a communications center to receive information, store, process and coordinate. (An advantage of this school is the promotion of modern communication methods. A disadvantage for this school is the risk of losing sight of material, human and financial resources.)

“Systemic Orientation”: describes management as a system of programs and methods of analysis to ensure high quality, with the interdisciplinary, analytical and synthetic explanation of processes and relationships, with the rational use of methods, languages, relationships. (This orientation is a synthesis of previous schools, being a result of increasing complexity. The basis of the ideas of this school is the concept of a system, which represents an ensemble of elements organized on the basis of interdependent links, whose functioning allows the achievement of some objectives).

“The Japanese Model”: Sums up more rules for achieving efficiency, performance: human-centered leadership and human relationships, emphasizing the role of training, culture, competence, value of people and their proper assessment, quality control. (With in this school, greater attention is paid, both at the company level and at the level of the organization of collectivism, to the detriment of individualism, which explains the important role of belonging to a community, a socio professional group, the cultivation of the resulting successful sentiment from joint activities, putting group interest sahead of the individual.)

“**Modern Leadership School**”: emphasizes as a priority idea the anchoring of managerial research in the field of concrete practice in order to provide managers with effective practical methods (Joita 2000, 19-20).

Regarding the evolution of the educational management, the specialists in the field distinguish several types of management, differentiated by the ability of the management acts to influence the educational process: linear, corrective, situational and investigative.

- ♦ **Linear management** is considered to be most appropriate for the activities of an educational unit, because the succession of the stages and their passing presents a very logical internal logic and an extremely precise temporal succession, dictated by the educational calendar. Within this type of management, the influence of the subjects is direct, the intermediate links are small or completely missing. Under such conditions, the means of process optimization are easy to mobilize, and the operating staff is largely highly qualified.
- ♦ **Corrective management** is also very important for the leadership of the school unit. Due to the large number of random factors influencing the results of the act and the educational process, there is a need for corrective measures at each stage. These are meant to optimize the interrelations in the educational process, which ensures the expected results.
- ♦ There is often a **situational management** in schools. School leadership is sometimes in the face of situations that they have not foreseen or that occurs unexpectedly. Thus, the manager is called upon to solve the problems that “cold” and may pose crisis situations.
- ♦ **Investigational management** implies a prospective attitude in the governing body of the school unit. This type of management is required at least in two situations: when circumstances call for a rapid research into the factors influencing the system, a situation followed by the need for an immediate decision; and when a broad foundation of a school decision is needed (Gherguț and Ceobanu 2008, 664).

In view of the above, one can say that the success and performance of a society depend on its education. Certainly this education means a lot of effort and it imposes many sacrifices.

Throughout history, each of the existing schools has contributed to the development of society, laying the foundations for contemporary management. The evolution of educational management therefore has a decisive role in changing society.

The school has been, is and will always be the environment in which the person involved in the educational process grows and educates properly for the requirements and the needs of society. School is the present and the future of the ever-changing society.

The priority action of the education system, as a component part of society, is to form man to be able to cope with real life. Therefore, Galina Martea (2013, 75) said: *“Every man’s work must be seen as a value and an investment for himself and for the whole society.”*

At a time when everything evolves rapidly, generating permanent changes, education must be an essential goal of society. In this respect, John Dewey (1907, 19-44) mentioned that: *“An ideal school must reflect an ideal society.”*

The level of development of a society depends to a large extent on capitalizing on human capital and investing in its development. Currently, school is the basic element that reflects the development of a society. The educational system, therefore directly highlights the level of living, culture and development of society.

In view of all this, the following must be taken into consideration:

- ✦ People’s integration into society is much easier and quicker when they are trusted.
- ✦ A person’s effectiveness depends more on the sense of responsibility and less on the control to which that person is subjected.
- ✦ Avoidance of uncertainty must be a constant of a society that is considered normal.
- ✦ As there is a fantastic potential to inform, educate and organize different activities within society, there is also a potentially harmful potential.

One can therefore notice a radical change in the way we communicate, how we inform, how we learn, how we negotiate, how we work. It all depends on how we use this fantastic potential we have.

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